

The Life of Peasants in Colonial Period told by U Ba Glay's Cartoons

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The art of cartoon occurred simultaneously with the journals and magazines in the world of journalism in Myanmar. The cartoons which produced in 1915 were drawn by Shwe Talay (a) Cartoonist Saya U Ba Glay. U Ba Glay recorded the Myanmar's social and political events with cartoons during 1915 and 1939 and also created the jolly type old man U Shwe Yoe in Myanmar's film and dramatic art.

U Ba Glay's cartoons were found in 1927 but they were not found in 1928, 1929 and 1930 in *Thuriya* Magazine and newspapers. However, U Ba Glay's cartoons were found again in 1931 and U Ba Glay had drawn the cartoons not only in the *Thuriya* Magazine and *Thuriya* newspaper but also in the *Myanma Alin* newspaper, it was found. U Ba Glay's cartoons were very active and lively together with the political situation of Myanmar because at that time, the situation of Myanmar was also unstable. During those years, the World Depression which attacked the capitalist world had also reached Myanmar and Myanmar had to face with unprecedented economic depression which led Myanmar to extreme poverty.

The peasants who were extremely poor economically were forced to collect the *Thathameda* Capitation tax of five kyats for one household and the peasants who could not afford to pay were tortured and arrested by the armed troops, police and bad *Thugyis*. Therefore, the peasants had lost their patience with the measures of the colonial government and rose against it with whatever arms they could possess and *Galon* Uprising occurred in December 1930. The peasants' Uprising was very important for Myanmar history. U Ba Glay also realized the conditions of the peasants clearly and he drew of cartoons concerning with the peasants throughout his life as a cartoonist. Therefore, the cartoons of U Ba Glay depicted the history of the peasants and they would be collected and printed until the outbreak of the peasants' revolution.

The earliest peasant cartoon among the discovered cartoons was the cartoon published in March 1918 *Thuriya* Magazine.

Figure 1

Figure 2

The cartoon shown in Figure 1 was depicted that the price of paddy was less as well as the production of paddy was less. But the expense of cultivation, tax and cost of consumption was big. Therefore, the peasant could not raise his head but the foreigner capitalist who would

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buy the paddy looked at the peasant satisfactorily by brushing his moustache. The price of paddy at that time was also depicted in U Ba Glay’s cartoon (Figure 2).

Although the price of paddy was one hundred and five kyats at that time, the peasants did not get the full price. It was the price given to their brokers in Yangon by the British capitalists who were exporting the paddy abroad. The peasant got only sixty-two kyats as the price of paddy at their villages. The price of paddy sixty-two kyats did not leave profit for the peasants and would even lose and if the peasants could not sell the entire paddy before monsoon season, the peasants would not have money to pay the tax as well as he must search the capital for the next season. U Ba Glay depicted the burden of tax of the peasants with the following cartoon (Figure 3).

The meaning of the cartoon was that although Myanmar and Indian were the same as the slave of the British colonialist, Myanmar peasant had to pay one tax more than the Indian peasant. That was the capitation tax in lower Myanmar and *Thathemeda* tax in Upper Myanmar. The capitation tax was five kyats per annum for one household of a peasant and two kyats eight peas for a grown up son and daughter. The capitation tax and *Thathemeda* tax collected in 1915-1916 at Myanmar was over 9.6 millions. As Myanmar was a province under the Indian Central Government, over three crores (or) thirty million kyats from the collected tax must be given per annum to the Indian Government. That was why U Ba Glay had drawn the cartoon to open the eyes of Myanmar that although Myanmar and Indian were the same as slaves under the British colonialists, Myanmar had to shoulder the yoke as a slave heavier than the Indian.

The conditions faced by Myanmar peasants at that time could be seen in the following cartoon. (Figure 4)

Figure 3

Figure 4

Bandoola Journal wrote the following words under the cartoon drawn by U Ba Glay.

လယ်သမားများသည် ဆင်းရဲဒုက္ခညံ့တွင်းက တက်နိုင်သည်မရှိ၊ နှစ်စဉ်ထာဝရ
 လယ်မှထွက်သောစပါးများနှင့် လယ်စောင့်နတ်မင်းကြီးများအား ပသနိုင်ရန် နေပူမှာကျောခင်း၍
 ရွံ့ဘွတ်တွင်းမှာ နွားနှင့်ဖက်ရုန်းနေကြရရှာ၏

When the paddy had been harvested after the Myanmar peasants worked together with the cattle, the British capitalists created the Bullinger Pool for the decline in the price of paddy. During the fall of the price of paddy, the Chettyars, landowners and creditors took away the paddy by measuring with big baskets leaving nothing for the poor peasants. The time when U Ba Galay returned to cartoon profession was the time of the Peasants’ Revolution. The news of

was risen to a certain extent and made the peasants to sell their paddy at the time of the good price for paddy and paid the taxes. Otherwise, the Government should permit the paying of paddy instead of cash as tax. In the peasant situation, the peasants had to sell their paddy with the least price and paid their debts to be paid to the Chettyars. The capitalists who bought the paddy gave the least price to the peasants who were drowned in debts. The Chettyars, the Government and the Capitalists were the same. The Chettyars were loaned by the banks of the British capitalists. It was said that the Government should always remember the 1930 Peasants' Revolution. The *Thathemeda* and the capitation taxes were demanded to be abolished. With this intention, U Ba Glay drew the following cartoon (Fig. 10). In this cartoon, it contained the two main causes of the outbreak of Galon Uprising. Only the suppression by the Government was left.

In conclusion, the difficulties of U Ba Glay to pave the new way of cartoon art were very large. At the beginning of the occurrence of cartoon, Myanmar viewers did not know how to appreciate the cartoon. But the power of cartoon was very large. It could express more vividly than the expression of words and writings and it had entered into Myanmar literary world. U Ba Glay depicted the lives of the peasants in the colonial period vividly with the art of cartoon.

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